

Exegetical Reading Ephesians 5:21-24: Implications For Women's Emancipation In Nigeria

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Abstract

The query and dissatisfaction of some liberationists against Christianity is the argument that it is an anti-feminist religion. God did not intend to initiate an unjust condition or create a discrepancy that would result to injustice or violence based on gender inequality. God had indeed wanted man to have dominion over all that he had created (Gen 1:27). It was man (male and female) in the sense of humanity was given the mandate of dominating the rest of creation. Prior to the coming of Christ, there was no uniformed position about women in the Jewish religion. It varied from time to time. The Pauline epistles especially Ephesians 5:21-24 seem to aggravate this perception; hence many still find Paul and his letters misogynist and responsible for the subordination of women. The research therefore focuses on interpreting the submission as taught by Paul in Ephesians 5: 21-24 in the context of the contemporary Nigerian society. The findings of the research points that none is lesser or higher, in quality of gender and therefore the issue of gender/sex, race and social strata should not de-emphasize the fact that all are co-workers in Christ and one. The exegetical method utilized revealed that the text is not an outright subjugating passage as reviled by many. None has to pick on this message in order to say that St. Paul was a misogynist or to blame Christianity as responsible for any form of subjugation and violence against women in our contemporary society. In order to achieve this, this research will go a long way to expose the purpose and values which the text bears for the women and the Christian family in general. The exegetical method of investigation will be used in the study and other literary works will be depended on as secondary method of data collection.

Keywords: *Exegesis, Women, Emancipation, Implication, Equality*

Introduction

At best in most ancient cultures of the world women are treated and regarded as second-class citizens. Sometimes they are only equivalent to properties which can be bought, a nuisance, the cause of deceit and failure to man. Many share this opinion because it was through her (woman) that Adam, the first man fell into sin. This perception remains unresolved in Nigeria till date. Gender inequality has become a cry on the lips of many and even more by the women. When one talks about the emancipation of women, it implies that there had been a situation of subjection and dependence because of the controlling influence of another. The state of this subordination and subjugation bears its root on the differences in gender. This difference exists in a society which had derived its concepts and ideas from the ancient cultures, women are perceived inferior. To some she is a necessary evil that has to be controlled and check mated else she becomes a danger

to the man. In Africa, women are victims of mentality that sees them as a thing instead of a person and as object of sexual pleasure instead of an equal partner (Chiegboka, 2012).

Currently, there is an overwhelming increase in the news of social crimes against women. Domestic violence and raping of women and children have taken over the news in many quarters in Nigeria since the famous Corona virus pandemic lockdown. The numerous dangers women face in the country has spurred many to question the cause of the problem. The Christian families and Church leaders are not immune to these sad stories. In the wake of these developments, there is rise in the number of academics, feminists, social media feminists, Non-Governmental Organizations and Government agencies that hope to curb this menace. In the bid to combat this, religion especially Christianity have punched and criticized as part of the problem. The African cultural background and a patriarchal system have been identified as reinforcement of these ill conditions of women. Eboh (2003) pointed of such cultural traits that mitigate the rights of women in Nigeria. In addition, Madunagu (2000) observed that “Politically, in modern Nigeria, the roles of women are negligible” (p. 133). This is to say, that the poor conditions of women extend to politics. The proportion of women in politics is not sufficient. There is much to be done. Chiegboka (2001) and Nmah (2003) bemoan the predicament of women in Igbo society. This is not peculiar to Igbo society, oppressive and unfavorable conditions burdens women in modern Nigeria.

Amongst many passages of the Bible that had referred to the woman as subordinate and lesser gender. The letters of Paul take the cake and is most disdainfully antagonized. Paul had enjoined the women as seen in 1 Cor. 14:34-35, Col. 3:18-19, 1 Tim. 2:9-15 and Eph 5:21ff to remain silent in the church, to subject themselves to their husbands, and to submit to their husbands who is the head of the family. Many of such feminists in discussing the causes of these ill situations have blamed Paul for aiding chauvinism, and subjugation of women especially that of Eph. 5-21-24 where Paul enjoined the wives to submit under the headship of the husband. Some of the Christian women in various denominations still see it as God’s will and plan that they should subjugated in their families. To them God has called women to be under the authority of their husbands. Quite so, but misinterpretation of the text (Eph. 5:21-24) has altered the true teaching and meaning of which the Apostle sought to pass across.

Antithetically to the pronounced opinion about Paul, one would find solace in his remark in Galatians 3:28 “that all are one in Christ, there is no slave or free, no Jew or Gentile and no male or female”. This very important teaching further explains clearly the already exemplary ways that

Jesus related with women in the Gospel. Eisler (1988) stated that “Jesus violated the androcentric customs of his time by talking openly with women” (p.28). The many examples of how Jesus overhauled such laws abound in the New Testament (Matt 15:22-28, Lk 13:16, Lk 7:35-8:5). Simply, Jesus did away with the age-long demeaning traditions of His people that are not in conformity with the demands and principles of the kingdom of God. Thus, Yanos (2001) sees Jesus as the first women’s liberator or liberator. Jewish tradition though did not allow the education of women, yet Jesus had women disciples along with the men. Evidently, these women were active in Jesus’ ministry as his disciples. As much as Jesus did not include any female apostle during His earthly mission, He had female supporters such as: Mary Magdalene, Joanna, Sussana and many others. These women with the twelve (12) apostles had been accounted for in Luke 8:1-3 as those who were with Jesus while He was preaching the good news. Obielosi (2015) observed that “From the gospels records, women enjoyed preeminent position in the life and ministry of Jesus. They were never regarded seriously as subordinates. They were active participants” (p. 66).

On the other hand, Paul lived in a different religious and political milieu. His core Jewish and legalistic background could also account for his strict positions about women sometimes. Often he follows the letters the acceptable household codes of then Roman world. However, Paul’s teaching in this very text should not be held responsible in its entirety for the subjugation of women. Submission *u`pota,ssw* as a word in the text implies “a voluntary act without coercion and done out of and for the love of God”. It is clearly not in any way subjugation and violence that we have in our today society meted out on women. This misinterpretation about the text must be addressed. Other than the unfitting misgivings about the teachings of Paul by many, there are more positive qualities of the admonishment of Paul in the text.

This work indeed is one of the recent scholarly researches in the area of theology of equality. It therefore hopes to be of immense help to those that wish to further divulge this subject in view. Most importantly, this work seeks to bring out the true value and roles of women in the Christian churches and in the Nigerian society. Hence emancipation for many of the women whose potentials are not utilized or had ignorantly locked up their potentials on the excuse of had been a woman. Sex or gender is neither an excuse nor a limit to the height a woman can attain. Again, a radical or an extreme approach by some feminists and scholars would reverse the truth of which the text intends as it regards to the women and the Christian family. By this, they fail to see the

otherwise meaning and purpose of the text. This exegetical revisiting of the text will to clear the clog that has discoloured the values of the passage.

Exegesis of the Text

We would attempt resolving the textual problems that the text under study bears. Next to this is the delimitation of the text.

Textual Criticism of Ephesians 5:21-24

Nestle –Aland presents this text as thus:

Ephesians 5:21-25 ²¹ ~Upotasso,menoi avllh,loij evn fo,bw| Cristou/(²²ai` gunai/kej toi/j ivdi,oij avndra,sin w`j tw/| kuri,w|(²³ o[ti avnh,r evstin kefalh. th/j gunaiko.j w`j kai. o` Cristo.j kefalh. th/j evkklhsi,aj(auvto.j swth.r tou/ sw,matoj\ gunai/kej toi/j ivdi,oij avndra,sin w`j ²⁴ avlla. w`j h` evkklhsi,a u`pota,ssetai tw/| Cristw/|(ou[twj kai. ai` gunai/kej toi/j avndra,sin evn panti,Å

The most problematic area of this passage is v.22, it reveals some textual difficulties. In this v.22, the phrase gunai/kej toi/j ivdi,oij avndra,sin w`j is witnessed in D⁴⁶,B Clement Theodore larcom. In Greek mss, it appears toi/j ivdi,oij in accusative. Another important change in this v.22 was made by one of the recent manuscripts, Jerome provided a parallel of this v.22, thus gunai/kej(u`pota,ssesqe toi/j ivdi,oij avndra,sin w`j..... The Jerome manuscript added an additional word to this v.22 the future indicative mood of the verb u`pota,ssw thus u`pota,ssesqe here it implies you will subject was included. This correction or addition was also seen in D F G It^d g^{txt}. Another parallel of this same v.22 which is gunai/kej toi/j ivdi,oij avndra,sin u`pota,ssesqe w`j.... is witnessed in 075 0150 424*(which is cited as of first order) also in 1852 1912 2200, this parallel is majority of recent manuscripts and probably corrected manuscripts and newer ones. Again alternation of this same v.22 made use of u`pota,ssesqeswsavn is placed as the second to the last word of the sentence before w`j by this u`pota,ssesqeswsavn command is inferred. This alternation is witnessed in 8 A I P Y 6 33 81 104 256 263 365 424 436 459 1175 1241 1319 1573 1739 1881 1962 2127 2464. Many other recent manuscripts have u`pota,ssesqeswsavn placed after gunai/kej

Obviously, in this analysis is the fact that our text had not added the various forms of the conjugation of the verb u`pota,ssw in the second part of v.22. This would probably be because it assumes that u`potasso,menoi in v.21 had transferred its meaning of “to subject” in v.22 Since κ A P which are older manuscripts had favoured an inclusion of an imperative mood of u`pota,ssw... . Here in our manuscript it is possible that the addition of u`pota,sseseqeswsavn and u`pota,ssesqe would have made the text ambiguous. However, the omission of the various conjugated forms of u`pota,ssw presents us with a more difficult reading (*lectio difficilor*), the more difficult the reading, the closer to the original manuscript. This text, although had presented us with difficult reading but it has poor attestation as the manuscript used was gotten from an earlier manuscript θ . We for the sole reason of poor attestation do not consider the text to be original.

Orientation of the Text

The exegetical analysis of the text, Eph 5:21-24 demands an understanding of the logic of this text. This is obtainable only when we mark out the text separately as an independent unit. The basic concern of this section of our work is to delimit the text in view. The background of this pericope, Eph 5:21-24 can be traced back to Eph 4:17-5:20. Contrary to first part of Eph 1-3, the second part from chapter 4 forms a new and independent unit. Quite distinct is the content and the exhortations of Eph 5. New characters, theme and a different narrative unit are obtained especially from vv.21-24. The concise message of this periscope had been elucidated upon.

Concurrently, Kizhakkeyil(2008) and Kobelski(2011) treated Eph 4:1-6:20 as a different structure of Ephesians which emphasize exhortation of worthy conduct or good behaviour. Kizhakkeyil(2008) also noted that Eph 4:17-5:20 as parentic sections which contrasts ungodly ways of Gentiles to the ethical implications of life in the body of Christ. He transcended from contrasting the Christian and the ungodly ways of the Gentiles to discussing the code of conduct for the household of God. Eph 5:21-24 bears a similarity with household codes of 1Pet 3:1-7 and that of Col 3:18-41. Again, truly to the position Kobelski(2011) “The codes depict the Christian household as hierarchically ordered social unit and may have served the function of responding to the Christians undermined the social fabrics by its advocating of equality among its adherents” (p. 890). The result of this accusation led to a response in the form of these household codes that goes along with the Christian conducts.

This can further be subdivided into primary and secondary parts. Eph 5:21 makes the first part while vv.22-24 make the latter. To show the distinctiveness of these parts or division, Lincoln (1990) had seen Eph 5:21 as a link completing the thought of that which had initially been exposed in Eph 5:18-20 about being filled with the spirit and at the same introducing a new topic, submission, which is to be developed in the rest of the passage. It is important to note therefore that the introductory function of v.21 is twofold. The admonition of v.22 depends on the participle of v.21 for its meaning.

Further, the idea of “fear” in the same v.21 would be completed in the later parts of the passage the secondary part is more like a clarification on the subject of submission especially at the realm of the family and dependent on the primary part. These two integral parts therefore make up the larger unit of Eph 5:21-33 that specifically dealt with desirable Christian conducts in the family. ~Upotasso,menoi was clearly and appropriately used by the author to express his ideas. In order to trace what informed the author’s idea of submission, Lincoln (1990) explains that the writer’s exhortation to marriage partners are clearly related to what he had said earlier in the letter about the relationship of Christ and the church. Paul’s view of the exalted Christ’s relationship to the church portrayed in Eph 1:20-23 colours his perspective on human relationships as well.

The Characters in Ephesians 5:21-24.

Christ (v.21), the wives (v.22), husbands (v.22) and the church (v.23). This text is also delimited by its meaning; the text depicts clearly a hierarchical social order whose ideal has been brought into the Christian family as its ideal. Be that as it may, this type of exhortation has not been seen outside the deutro-canonical epistles and the first letter of Peter.

Presentation of a Working Translation

We would propose here a working translation like thus: **21** Be subject to one another in fear of Christ, **22** the wives to one’s own husbands as to the Lord, **23** for man is the head of the woman even as Christ head of the church himself savior of the body, **24** but as the church subject to Christ thus and the wives to the husbands in all things.

Semantic Analysis

The style of this text is very unique and rich, from a well based premises it arrived to its logical conclusion of its argument and admonition. A proper interpretation of this text would require an in depth understanding of the major key words found in this text. The verbs, both the main and subordinate clauses are individually explained and briefly commented on. The sentence is also given a technical clarification at the points were needful. The passage although with four verses but they all embedded in a singular sentence. Thus beginning with v.21, this analysis of the text ensues, verse after to v.24.

V.21

Main Verbal Clause: Upotasso,menoi avllh,loij evn fo,bw | Cristou

Parsing/ comment: Upotasso,menoi this is the, 2nd person plural, present indicative, passive voice of the verb u`pota,ssw.. This can also be described as a verb participle but here it this verb participle functions like verb. The voice of the verb is not active and again the verb is present in its meaning. Upotasso,menoi being in the plural position means that the act of subjecting is shared by the subjects (husband and wife) implied by the sentence. Thus the main verbal clause which carries the meaning of the whole sentence already by pluralizing the verb tells that it is not singularly for either of the subjects but for both of them simultaneously.

By subjecting to one another, it is not subjugation (to forcibly impose obedience or servitude) but from our positive understanding of the word “fear” as used by Paul in the passage one can say that this act of subjecting is also of a positive one. Hence it is a voluntary and a willful subjecting, that which is not imposed by either of the subjects of the sentence, the wife willfully subjects to the husband and vice versa. Such understanding therefore tells that subjugation or forceful imposition of obedience or servitude had not been implied by the sentence. Christ who is an embodiment of perfect love cannot be associated with any form of inhumane character in the institution of marriage.

evn fo,bw | Cristou, fo,bw; this is the dative, masculine, singular of the noun fo,boj. This noun connotes the meaning of fear or terror. The word “fear” means to venerate, to feel awe towards something , negatively fear could mean to regret, to frighten, also a strong , uncontrollable, unpleasant emotion caused by actual or perceived danger or threat. The scripture is filled with

examples of how the term “fear of God” is a positive value rather than a negative one. Often the fear of God has the meaning of “to venerate” or “to feel awe towards something”. Especially in the Old Testament, the instances for this abound, Joseph had won the trust of his brothers when he declared that he is a God-fearing man (Gen 42:18). Likewise, Shiprah and Puah in Ex 1:17, because they feared God spared the Hebrew babies. In Ex18:21, Moses chose leaders to help him on the basis that they feared God and wouldn’t take bribes. Also, because the Israelites feared God, they treated the disabled and the elderly well (Lev 19:14, 32).

In the New Testament, Jesus had enjoined the people “not to be afraid of those who want to kill your body, for they cannot touch your soul, but fear only God who can destroy both soul and body in hell” (Matthew 10:28). Further, in 2Cor 7:1 Paul admonished Christians to work towards complete holiness because we fear God. Thus while discussing sin in Rom 3:18, Paul said “There is no fear of God before their eyes”. Further, 1John 4:18 had indicated that perfect love expels all fear. By expelling fear, the subject “fear” is casted in its negative understanding. Consequently, “in fear of Christ” as Paul puts it in Eph 5:21, aligns more to the positive aspect and meaning of fear. Subjecting to one another in the situation of marriage would simply be in reverence of Christ and not by subjugation which probably a negative understanding of the phrase.

Cristou, this is genitive, masculine, and singular of the noun Cristoj. The word means saviour or the anointed one; though the genitive masculine singular of a definite article had been attached to the word it inherently displays the usage here and it therefore indicates belongingness.

V.22

Subordinate Clause: ai` gunai/kej toi/j ivdi,oij avndra,sin w`j tw/| kuri,w

gunai/kej- vocative feminine plural of the noun gunh, ivdi,oij- dative masculine plural of the adjective ivdi,oij. avndra,sin- dative masculine plural of the noun avnhr, , w`j- this is a conjunction that connotes subordinate meaning “as”. This phrase here is not just appositional to v.21; but it explains further the content of the previous verse. Together with the first verse it expresses the degree of the action. To subject in fear of Christ, the wives to one’s own husbands as to the Lord.

V.23

Subordinate Clause: o[ti avnh,r evstin kefalh. th/j gunaiko.j

Subordinate Clause: w`j kai. o` Cristo.j kefalh. th/j evkklhsi,aj(auvto.j swth.r tou/ sw,matoj

Parsing/comment: evkklhsi,aj – genitive feminine singular of the noun evkklhsi,a meaning church or assembly. As Nmah (2012) rightly noted that “The church is the called out people of God who constitutes the holy presence of Christ in the world” (p.72). Auvto.j - nominative masculine singular of the pronoun or an adjective auvto.j. As an adjective it means “same” but as a pronoun as used in the sentence it means “himself”. Swth.r – nominative masculine singular meaning saviour. Sw,matoj – genitive neuter singular of the noun sw,ma. Thus “and as Christ head of the head himself saviour of the body” this given clause expresses the degree of the action and augments the theme of submission.

V.24

Subordinate Clause: avlla. w`j h` evkklhsi,a u`pota,ssetai tw/| Cristw/|(ou[twj kai. ai` gunai/kej toi/j avndra,sin evn panti,Å

Parsing/comment: 3rd person singular present indicative passive voice of the verb u`pota,ssw. It expresses again the state of being under control. : avlla. – This is a conjunction meaning “but” or except. ou[twj- - this is an adjective or an adverb and here it means thus. avndra,sin – dative masculine plural of the noun avndr. panti, - dative neuter singular of the adjective or pronoun. pa`j and it means all or all things.

A Critic of the Head and Body in Ephesians

The text Eph 5: 21-24 is one of the Deutro-Pauline teachings on the family. In the bid of admonishing and distinguishing between the Christian conduct that is worthy of been emulated and the Gentile conduct. Transcending from this exhortation, the author from Eph 5:21 pay special emphasis on the union of the husband and wife in the Christian circle. This teaching here takes a different dimension from that observed in some other Pauline corpus also in 1Peter. In some other New Testament passages where there were similar household admonitions, only women’s submissions were noted. There were no thorough argument that led to their conclusions, thus only their conclusions and positions towards the subject of marriage relationships were outlined.

Contrary to these situations observed above, using kefalh. (head) and sw,ma (body) Paul makes a connection with his theme of submission Eph 5:23 o[ti avnh,r evstin kefalh. th/j gunaiko.j w`j kai. o` Cristo.j kefalh. th/j evkklhsi,aj(auvto.j swth.r tou/ sw,matoj\ Some scholars had argued that since Ephesians is a deuterocanonical book it has a distinct content different from the established Pauline books. Thus Kizhakkeyil (2008) argued that while this letter speaks of the church as the bride of Christ, Paul is silent on this point. Kobelski (2011) also noted that “In Greco-Roman literature as here in Ephesians, the household code of conduct treated relations between husbands and wives...as relationships of subordinate to superiors”(p.890). Our interest here is that the household code as seen in Eph 5:21-24 was seen to have been adapted from the Greco-Roman philosophy by New Testament authors to assist in the moral instruction of Christians.

Be that as it may, Paul drew a vivid comparison with the “head” in order to buttress his point here. He did not get this idea from nowhere rather his Old Testament and Jewish understanding of head. Different periods of time especially from the Jewish world reflect its peculiar understanding and usage of the word “head” or “kefalh”. It is worthy to note that in Ephesians, a heightened New Testament reflections and usage of the term “the body of Christ” was found. In Ephesians as well, there is the largest concentration of the usage of bodily parts and members such as the head and the body was also seen. Some other images that Paul used in this epistle include the bride and the temple.

Therefore, it is very important that we set forth Paul’s understanding of the head and the body metaphors as he used them in the passage. This would be against the background of his usage of these metaphors in his other epistles also in the context of the Old Testament, Hellenistic and New Testament backgrounds. Thus, we would render explanation as why he used the word “head” to compare to Christ also to the husbands and why he used the word to describe the relationship between Christ and the church in Ephesians. This metaphor “o[ti avnh,r evstin kefalh. th/j gunaiko.j w`j kai. o` Cristo.j kefalh. th/j evkklhsi,aj” in Eph 5:23 is peculiar.

In some passages in the Pauline corpus and in New Testament, it does not take this exact and direct comparison. By inference, Christ head of the church himself saviour of the body in this passage indicates that the head which is Christ saves the body, the church. Eph 5:21-24 also made use of an epithet, the body of Christ. This was used to describe the church. This phrase “body of

Christ” includes the idea of wholeness, the inter-relationship of the members and the self identity of each individual. Passages like 1Cor 11:3 outlined Paul’s usage of the head and body images, and some others expressed the church as unity or body with the members having diverse functions (1Cor 12 : 31, Eph 2:11-22, 4 :1-16,Gal 3:26-29). There are still some other passage that described Jesus as the head of the church and the church as his body (Eph 1:22-23, 2:19-22, 5:21-32).

Kefalh in the New Testament and Paul’s Thought

Many of the New Testament passages outside the Pauline corpus had at one point or other used the kefalh, but not in the special way Paul had made use of the word his epistles. Balz (2000) posited that “The meaning of kefalh as a leader, chief, master which is attested for in the Hebrew and Aramaic equivalents and mediated through Hellenistic Judaism (LXX, Philo) allows Paul in 1Cor 11:3ff the combine the sociological fact of ancient patriarchal system with theological idea of origin and rule.

A critical look at 1Cor 11:3 would help us understand the meaning of kefalh especially as used by Paul in his letters. 1 Corinthians 11:3 qe,lw de. u`ma/j eivde,nai o[ti panto.j avndro.j h` kefalh. o` Cristo,j evstin(kefalh. de. gunaiko.j o` avnh,r(kefalh. de. tou/ Cristou/ o` qeo,j. The translation of this scripture would give “But I wish you know that the head of every man is Christ, but the man head of a woman and God head of Christ”. One can draw a comparison to a similar argument of Paul in Eph 5:21-24, especially v.23 o[ti avnh,r evstin kefalh. th/j gunaiko.j w`j kai. o` Cristo.j kefalh. th/j evkklhsi,aj(auvto.j swth.r tou/ sw,matoj\ gunai/kej toi/j ivdi,oij avndra,sin w`j . As he had argued that” the husband is the head of the wife even as Christ head of the church himself saviour of the body. Hence one may be fast to draw conclusion that these comparisons indicate superiority or the subordination of one over another. The last part of 1Cor 11:3, “God, head of Christ) really helps us to explain the meaning of the other parts of the sentence. For one to say that God is superior to Christ automatically says that Christ is inferior in essence and divine nature. Such interpretation and position that places God higher than Christ is incorrect as it goes against the hypostatic union found in Christ.

Further, just as Bromiley (1995) noted, it is not as if Paul was individualizing kefalh.-sw,ma concept of Gnosticism. He is using the term kefalh. as it appeals to him. Paul could have used avrch, as it sometimes appears in LXX, if there had not been a closer personal relationship in

kefalh.. One may seem to note that along further arguments, what follows 1Cor 11:3 forms the basis for the discussion of the problem of the head covering in the Corinthian worship. With regards to this 1Cor 11:3ff, Balz (2000) argued that Paul's intention is clear, women must cover their heads, but men are not to wear head coverings. By nature the man and woman are not distinct and this expressed in the veiling of her head.

Paul and the Metaphor of the Body

It is not surprising that we can find in Eph 5:21-24, that the apostle Paul refers to Christ as the saviour of the body. As we had already pointed out, the epistle of Paul to the Ephesians is prevalent in its usage of the word body (sw/ma) to qualify the body of Christ. Paul's constant usage of the theme of sw/ma just like kefalh did not just come to be. It has its various derivations which informed his usage of sw/ma., such as the following: The Old Testament and LXX, the post-New Testament period, the Greek world and the New Testament. The New Testament, especially John introduced a different meaning for the word. This personalization of the body was carried on Paul in his letters. The Church became the body of Christ.

The New Testament: The word "sw/ma" was used 142 times in the New Testament. It appears 91 times in the Pauline corpus which is more than 50 percent of its entire usage in the New Testament. This was never used for organic body and the Pauline letters bear the true content of the word especially in Colossians and Ephesians. Again the word "Sw/ma" has the traditional or the technical use of corpse or slave. Its meaning "corpse" as used in the New Testament usually refers to the body of Jesus (Mk 15; 43, Matt 27:59; 24:3, John 19:3 and 20:12). John 2:21 present another understanding of sw/ma, here Jesus spoke of the temple of his body. This was different from some other meaning of sw/ma in the New Testament, corpse or slave as seen in Rev 18:13. By the temple of his body, Jesus had meant his dead and resurrected body.

Relationship between the church and Christ is that of intimate communion just like that of husband and wife. Thus between the head and body in Ephesians is an intimate relationship and mutuality. The church is a universal phenomenon, embodying all creation and the body of Christ which include Christians. The members of the church are solely united through faith and baptism. Utmost, the fullness (plh,rwma), flows from the head down to the other members of the body.

Implication of the Emancipative Elements of the Text for the Nigerian Women

As already stated, the interest of the research is to unveil those unpopular values of the texts. It presents unexplored grounds useful for women in Nigeria aside the chauvinist impression. The first of these mutual emancipative elements in the text is mutual submission. Paul before emphasizing on the code of conduct for the family had first enjoined the Christians in V.21 to mutually subject to one another without regard to gender. This ~Upotasso,menoi appears to be the controlling verb in the entire pericope as it carries the main verb of the text. Thus v.22 does not contain any verb, it leans on the verb ~Upotasso,menoi in v.21 for its meaning: “Being subject to one another in the fear of Christ. The wives to their own husbands as unto Lord”. This rightly represents equal right of both men and women in the Christian community. Since Fiorenza (1983) brilliantly proves also that Jesus established a discipleship of equals (Jn.15:15), in line with this position, it implies that the principles of mutual subjection had been provided for a Christian community of equals. The members of the community are expected to submit to one another regardless of gender.

Pauline theology in no small way had contributed to human rights and the emancipation of women in our society. Contemporary Nigerian women are empowered by this passage to exist in a state of mutual subjection with others in the society. Women are to not just exist but to live out their God given potentials. Thus their marital state does not equate them as sub humans. They are to subject to their husbands in fear of Christ. In this mutuality, the husbands are to love their wives as Christ loved the church. By this, submission does not call for subjugation or violence and abuse against the women. It is also the duty of the Church and the state to put functional laws in action to further strength the place of women. The Church can be more proactive in teaching the rights of individuals while using its theology.

Second emancipative element in Eph 5:21-24 is the precise limitation that is placed on the analogy of the husband and Christ. In the manner the church submits to Christ is such which the women are to submit to their husband. The husband’s self-emptying as Christ did for the church is required here. This therefore connotes deliberate self-sacrifice, “husbands; love your wives, just as Christ loved the church”. The typical model of self-emptying for the Christian husbands is explained by Paul again in Phil. 2:5-8: Christ who was in the form of God did not count himself equal with God. He gave up the privileges of divinity, and took up voluntary servant hood and obedience to God even to the points of death. The exposition given by Paul in the text is a model

the Christian family ought to operate. From such an understanding the act of submission is a sacrificial one and so is the self-emptying of Christ or the husband. Giving up privileges is not prerogative of the wives but is more so required of the husbands. The contemporary Nigerian women should explore the meaning and value of the text for its benefit. The Christian community becomes unified and fulfilling from the in-depth examples and lessons from Paul's message.

Finally, the last of the emancipative elements in the passage is the concept of the organic oneness between the husband as the head and the wife as body. For the husband is the head of the wife just as Christ is the head of the church, the body of which Christ is the saviour's v. 23. As we had already explained above kefalh may mean "source". Scholars like Mollenkott (2003) argue that "the word head is never connected with the intelligence" (p.50). The ancient Hebrew was unaware of the function of the brain and indeed had no name for it, the intellectual powers were believed to be situated in the heart as Prov.4:23 states "Keep your heart with all vigilance; for from it flows the springs of life" (c.f. Matt. 9:4, Mk7:21). The heart was understood to be the seat of a human being's entire psychic life, including the emotions, the intellect, the volition, moral life, and the point of contact with God.

For the author of the text, the husband as the head of the wife is more referring to him being the source and not necessarily the arbiter head. Such a position of men more often than not gives the woman value and a place in the family. As Christ is the source of the church, so the husband who empties himself of patriarchal privileges is the source of the Christian family structure. The head and the body are one. These imageries or metaphors indicate the organic oneness of the head and the rest of the bodily parts. Obviously, Paul had taught in Eph 5:29 that "for no man ever hates his own flesh, but nourishes and cherishes it as Christ does the church because we are members of his body". Mollenkot (2003) points that "the analogy of wifely submission to husbandly headship in everything is very much limited by what we know about the way Christ and the church are related to one another, in an utterly non-coercive voluntary pattern" (p. 46). Paul does not use the active mode, as he does when describing God's subjugation of the principalities and powers. He rather for Christian submission uses the passive mode in order to describe a voluntary attitude of giving in, cooperating, assuming responsibility and carrying a burden intended by the text.

Without doubt, the organic oneness or unity of the text proves to be a source of emancipation for the Nigerian women. If the husband and wife in the matrimony of marriage are made whole like that of the head and body then the head cannot do without the body likewise the

body cannot do without the head. There is no need for the woman to feel inferior, as she is necessary for the sustenance of the unity and happiness of the marriage. Since God has made them one, she is important and has qualitative roles to play in the family, church and the society at large. These emancipative elements in Eph.5:21-24 would in no small measure help the Nigerian women and the society at large to re-examine the position and roles of women. It would therefore help to develop themselves and contribute meaningfully to the family and the society as Paul and his teachings empowered them to do so. Obielosi (2015) argued that “Since the society thrives through separation of powers and checks and balances, the family, a microcosmic society and God’s household must also have separation of powers for there to be marital unity” (p.70).

Evaluation and Conclusion

Pauline thoughts about women are undeniably laced with unflattering opinions and chauvinistic descriptions. This research however posits that there are uncovered treasures of the text that is valuable in affecting women in Nigeria. Interpretations that support subjugation of wives and women alone are not appropriate. There are other positive ways to appreciate the text in the Christian household and externalize it to the general society. The mutual submission of the members of the community and the Christ’s love analogy in the text are vital to refute any support for oppression of women. Organic wholeness of the head and body for the fullness and unity of the family is intended. The Nigerian society needs solutions to these many oppressive systems against women in today society. The female child must no longer be seen as less important and subservient if the country must move forward. Exegetical revisit of the text has unraveled loving headship and voluntary submission by the husband and wife as superior to a forceful and dominating position. Transcending beyond popular bias here as done in the research has revealed a better way of understanding Paul and his views about women in his letters. This has emancipative implications for women in Nigeria.

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